

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

RESEARCH OF HUMIC ACIDS IN THE COMPOSITION OF SOME COALS OF THE REPUBLIC OF TAJIKISTAN

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ABSTRACT

This article presents the results of an experimental analysis on the study of humic acids in the composition of some coals of the Republic of Tajikistan. During the studies, coal samples from the Shurob, Fon-Yagnob, Ziddi, Sayod, Nazar-Ailok and Kurtegin deposits were selected as the object of research. To isolate humic acids from the composition of the studied coal samples, the analyzed samples were first dehydrated and bitumen was removed. Humic acids were isolated from prepared coal samples by extraction with an alkaline solution of pyrophosphate (Na₄P₂O₇). Using methods of organic chemistry and methods of physicochemical analysis, a qualitative and quantitative analysis of humic acids in the studied coal samples was carried out. As a result, it was established that coal samples from the Shurob, Fon-Yagnob, Ziddi, Sayod, Nazar-Ailok and Kurtegin deposits contain 22.66%, 15.40%, 16.50 %, 9.54%, 16.60%, 13.19%, respectively, humic acids.

Keywords: coal, coal deposits, Shurob, Fon Yagnob, Ziddi, Sayad, Nazar-Ailok, Kurtegin, analysis, extraction, pyrophosphate method, humic acids.

Introduction

Humic acids have found their practical application in various industries. One of the reasons why humic acids are practically not used in the pharmaceutical industry largely depends on their biological activity.

On the basis of these biologically active compounds, specialists in the field of medicine and pharmacy have developed several names of medicines, the use of which regulates the normal activity of the digestive organs.

Humic acids have been found to have antioxidant and antifungal properties. In this regard, on the basis of these organic compounds, the production of a number of antiviral drugs has been established. Biologically active substances are produced based on the compositions of humic substances to regulate the regeneration and growth of platelets, erythrocytes and platelets in the blood.

Sodium salts of humic acids are used as additional nutrients in animal feed, which helps to increase their weight. Nitrogenous acids increase hormones in the body of animals, which leads to an increase in their growth.

It is known that Tajikistan's coal reserves amount to 0.0043 trillion tons, most of which are estimated to be of medium and low quality. It has been established that the use of medium and low quality coal as a fuel has a strong negative impact on the ecology of the area [1-4].

For this reason, the use of coal as a raw material in production, especially humic acids, not only benefits the economy of the Republic of Tajikistan, but also prevents environmental damage and helps reduce greenhouse gas emissions into the atmosphere [3, 5].

Linseed is one of the oldest oilseeds and is grown in more than 50 countries. The meaning of flaxseed in Latin is "very useful". Currently, the main areas of flax seed cultivation are located in the northern hemisphere, including Canada, Mainland China, America, India, and Ethiopia. Among these countries are Canada and mainland China is the largest exporter, accounting for more than 30% of the flaxseed trade (6).

In this regard, the subject of research and research of humic acids, the determination of their amount in the composition of coal is one of the relevant topics of

modern science of organic chemistry and physical chemistry.

In scientific sources, humic acids refer to humic substances. These organic compounds belong to humic

substances and have a high reactivity. The reason why humic acids have such chemical properties is that they contain functional groups in their molecule-COON⁻, -CO⁻, -OH, NH₂ and NH.

Formula 1. The structural formula of humic acids of the soil composition.

Studies conducted by scientists and researchers in the field of organic chemistry and physical chemistry have shown that these natural organic compounds have a very complex structure (Formula 1).

As follows from the proposed formula (Formula 1) in the humic acid molecule, in addition to the functional groups-COOH, -CO⁻, -OH, NH₂, NH, there are charcoal residues, heterocyclic compounds and aromatic compounds. The presence of such a molecular structure in these organic compounds contributes to the fact that the human body decreases when exposed to ecotoxicants such as heavy metals and radionuclides.

It should be noted here that humic acids have a complex structure and may differ in their physical properties [5-7].

According to the solubility properties, humic acids can be divided into three groups.

1. Humic acids are practically insoluble in acids and alkalis.
2. Humic acids are soluble in alkali solutions.
3. Humic acids are fulvic acids that are soluble in acid solution.

Based on the analysis of industry literature, it was found that photosynthesis plays an important role in the

formation of humic acids. The second stage of the formation of humic acids is associated with the decomposition of components of plant raw materials, resulting in the formation of humic substances [3, 10].

It should be noted here that humic acids are found not only in the composition of coal, but also in the composition of water, soil and peat. It has been established that the content of the elements oxygen, nitrogen, carbon and hydrogen in the composition of humic acids isolated from water, soil, peat and coal differs from each other.

The molecular structure of humic acids has not been fully studied [3, 10]. The exact structure of humic acids does not exist, so these organic compounds are considered in their multistructural form, at the molecular level and with the properties of functional groups.

One of the most important chemical properties of humic acids is the ability of these chemical compounds to react with other substances. It is due to the presence of functional groups-COOH, -o, -CO and aromatic radicals that these compounds can actively participate in ionic, donor-acceptor and hydrophobic reactions [6-9]. Table 1 shows the dependence of the physico-chemical properties of humic acids on the presence of functional groups.

Table 1.

Dependence of the chemical properties of humic acids on the functional groups of their molecular composition

Functional groups	Chemical properties
COOH	Ion exchange reaction
CA – OH	Complexation reaction
$>C = O$	Redox reaction
C ₆ H ₆	Donor-acceptor reaction
CH _n	The reaction of the hydrophobic effect

Based on the analysis of industry literature and the study of the physico-chemical properties of humic acids, the goal was set: to study humic acids in the composition of some coals of the Republic of Tajikistan, such as coal "Shurob", "Nazar-Aylok", "Von Yagnob", "Zidi", "Sayed" and "Kurtegin".

To isolate humic acids from the composition of the studied coal samples, we used the extraction method

[7]. We used an ammonia solution of potassium alkali as an extractant. This technique led to the release of humic acids from the composition of coal samples and their conversion into potassium salts. This method of separating humic acids is called the pyrophosphate method in the industry literature. The methodology and technology of this experimental analysis are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Method and technology of humic acid extraction from the composition of the studied coal samples by the pyrophosphate method

As can be seen from the method and technology of separating humic acids from the composition of the studied coal samples shown in Figure 1, bitumen and bitumen were used to isolate the used coal samples "Shurob", "Von Yagnob", "Zidi", "Sayed", "Nazar-Aylak" and "Kurtegin" [8-10].

Materials and methods

To isolate water from the studied composition of coal, the analyzed samples were carried out using drying cabinets at a temperature of 100 - 106°C for 60 minutes. The analyzed samples were then cooled using a desiccator and the mass of the dehydrated coal samples was determined by weighing on an analytical scale.

In order to isolate bituminous compounds from the composition of the analyzed coal samples, we ground the dehydrated coal to a size of 0.2-0.3 and extracted using steamed toluene. The amount of bitumen was determined as a percentage by the difference in the mass of the analyzed coal samples before and after extraction.

To determine the ash content of the analyzed coal samples, we take 20 grams from each sample in a crucible and keep them in a muffle furnace, which has a temperature of 700-800°C for 3 hours. After that, we cooled the samples and weighed them using analytical Scales.

Humic acids were then isolated from the prepared coal samples by extraction with an alkaline solution of pyrophosphate ($\text{Na}_4\text{P}_2\text{O}_7$).

To isolate humic acids, samples of the analyzed coal "Shurob", "Von Yagnob", "Zidi", "Sayed", "Nazar-Aylak" and "Kurtegin", from which bitumen and water were removed separately in the flask (a) (see Fig.1) and treated with an alkaline solution of pyrophosphate ($\text{Na}_4\text{P}_2\text{O}_7$)₂ [$(\text{Na}_4\text{P}_2\text{O}_7 + \text{NaOH} + \text{H}_2\text{O})$], they were mixed with a magnetic mixer for 15 minutes. Then the solution was separated from the mixture by filtration and transferred to another flask (flask B). The remainder of the mixture, which will be obtained in the form of a colloidal suspension solution, was centrifuged, resulting in a precipitate.

To clean the formed sediment from other deposits, we washed it several times with a solution equal to 1% Na, and the resulting solution was transferred to the second flask (flask B).

After performing these actions, a dilute solution was poured from the second flask (flask B) into a flask with a volumetric porosity of 1000 ml-and until the specified volume was reached, it was filled with evaporated water. We took 100 ml of the prepared solution and transferred it to a cone-shaped flask with a volumetric porosity of 250 ml-A. by titration with a 5% NSL solution, the hydrogen index of the solution was increased to pH 3.0.

This technique led to the fact that humic acids from the composition of the studied coal samples separated from the solution into a sedimentary form. The falling sediment is dried to determine its mass.

Then the isolated humic acids were individually burned in a muffle furnace at a temperature of 750-8000C, the ash mass was determined.

To determine the mass of coal from smokeless coal, we used the following formula:

$$m_y = m_3 \frac{100 - (W^a + A^a)}{100} \quad (1)$$

In the Formula:

m_3 is the mass of the analyzed coal, g;

W^a is the mass fraction of water (analytical humidity) in the composition of coal with score %;

A^a is the ash content of the sample of the analyzed coal, calculated as %.

The total weight of the isolated humic acids (m_x) and the yield of humic acids from the composition of the analyzed samples of untreated and untreated coal as a percentage were calculated using the following formula:

$$m_x = \frac{100 \cdot v(m_1 - m_2)}{V_1 \cdot m}$$

In The Formula:

m_x - is the total mass of the analyzed humic acids;

m_1 - is the mass of humic acids after drying, g;

m_2 - is the mass of ash formed from humic acids,;

V - is the volume of the alkaline solution used, cm^3 ;

V_1 - is the total volume of the alkali solution, aliquots, for the precipitate humic acids, cm^3 .

Results and discussions

The results of the analysis of the determination of humic acids in the composition of coal samples "Shurob", "Von Yagnob", "Zidi", "Sayed", "Nazar-Aylok" and "Kurtegin" are presented in Table 2.

Table 2.

Quantitative analysis of humic acid content in one coal sample of the Republic of Tajikistan

Sample of analyzed coal	Quantity, %				
	Analytical humidity	The ash content	Bitumen content	Yield of humic kilotons	Ash humic acid
Shurob	11.29	10.01	11.10	22.66	5.94
Background-Yagnob	19.00	2.58	18.18	15.40	0.8
Against	19.72	2.68	7.14	16.50	4.37
Nazar-Aylak	2.66	2.60	2.04	9.54	0.26
Syed	6.90	16.40	15.21	16.60	0.04
Kurtegin	9.80	3.05	3.62	13.19	0.25

As can be seen from the results of the quantitative analysis of the humic acid content in a unit of coal samples of the Republic of Tajikistan presented in Table 2, humic acids in the analyzed samples have different densities. The largest amount of humic acids was found in the composition of coal from the Shurob deposit, which is 22.66%. A significant amount of humic acids was also found in the analyzed samples.

Conclusion

Thus, humic acids in the composition of coal deposits "Shurob", "Von Yagnob", "Zidi", "Sayed", "Nazar-Aylok" and "Kurtegin" were enhanced using methods of organic protection and physico-chemical analysis. The study revealed that the content of humic acids from different coal sources from local places is

able to widely use as an agent against toxicants in ecosystems and medicine.

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